

[white paper]

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Ultrannumbers

Open Mathematics Collaboration*†

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Abstract

We introduce a set of abstract objects, the so-called ultrannumbers, in order to generalize different classes of numbers. The idea is to find equations with nonexistent solutions in the original set, and then use them to extend the numerical system.

keywords: ultrannumbers, complex numbers, quaternions, octonions, dual numbers, number theory

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/jrqax/download>
<https://zenodo.org/record/7749414>

Note

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*All authors with their affiliations appear at the end of this white paper.

†Corresponding author: mplobo@uft.edu.br | **Open Mathematics Collaboration**

Introduction

3. This is intended to be a pedagogical article.
4. Although we introduce new terminology, our focus remains on presenting a novel perspective for constructing distinct numerical systems.
5. As an introduction to our discussion, we define **ultranumbers** as *abstract objects* that *generalize various sets of numbers*.
6. We show two examples—dual numbers and complex numbers—as particular instances of first-order ultranumbers.

First-order ultranumbers ($\mathcal{U}_n^1(F)$)

7. Let $a, b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots, b_n \in \mathbb{R}$ and $m, n \in \mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.
8. We define $\mathcal{U}_0^1 = \mathbb{R}$.
9. The set of *first-order ultranumbers* is then defined by

$$\mathcal{U}_n^1(F) = \{a + b_1u_1 + b_2u_2 + b_3u_3 + \dots + b_nu_n \mid \exists F \nexists v_{n-m} \in \mathcal{U}^{n-1} \setminus A\}$$

where $v_{n-1} = a + b_1u_1 + b_2u_2 + b_3u_3 + \dots + b_{n-1}u_{n-1}$, $1 \leq m < n$, and $F = \{f(v_{n-m}) = 0\}$ is a nonempty set of equations.

Dual numbers ($\mathbb{D}$)

10. $[1, 2]$
11. Let $n = 1$, $A = \{0\}$, $m = 1$, and $F_d = \{f_d(x) = x^2 \mid x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus A\}$.
12. We have that $\nexists x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus A : x^2 = 0$.
13. Hence

$$\mathcal{U}_1^1(F_d) = \mathbb{D}.$$

Complex numbers ($\mathbb{C}$)

14. Let $n = 1$, $A = \emptyset$, $m = 1$, and $F_c = \{f_c(x) = x^2 + 1 \mid x \in \mathbb{R}\}$.

15. We have that $\nexists x \in \mathbb{R} : x^2 = -1$.

16. Hence

$$\mathcal{U}_1^1(F_c) = \mathbb{C}.$$

Quaternions ($\mathbb{H}$)

17. We leave for the reader to prove that $\mathcal{U}_4^1(F_h) = \mathbb{H}$.

Octonions ($\mathbb{O}$)

18. We leave for the reader to prove that $\mathcal{U}_8^1(F_o) = \mathbb{O}$.

Higher-orders ultranumbers

19. The purpose of defining higher-order ultranumbers, denoted as $\mathcal{U}_i^j(F)$, is to provide a framework for extending the concepts and reasoning used in various numerical systems [3, 4].

Final Remarks

20. Discovering isomorphisms between distinct sets of ultranumbers would provide valuable insights.

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [5, 6].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Supplementary files

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [7, 8].

How to cite this paper?

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The Open Mathematics Collaboration

Matheus Pereira Lobo¹ (lead author, mplobo@uft.edu.br)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4554-1372>

¹Federal University of Northern Tocantins (Brazil)